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“LINGERING HURT: FINDING HOPE IN THE PROMISE OF HIM”

The clock ticks so slowly day by day.

I wonder when it will be.

The day we can altogether say,

“We are happy as a family”.

It pains to think about the past,

Each hurtful moment lingers in my heart.

When will be that perfect day?

Trust me, I never wanted you to run away.

Oh, I wish there was a way

To turn back the hands of time,

So I could have given you more,

And you won't have to go and shut the door.

I didn't meant for things to go this bad,

All I wanted was to ensure,

That she won't quietly steal you,

For I know that you've fallen for her too.

Our love has gone wrong

Just like what we hear on a song

You hate me that much

Thinking I planned all this to give you a scratch!

You might have thought

That I was the “gone girl” who got mad.

I may have that sarcastic look

But inside me is still the “Pirl” you once took.

In the countless sleepless nights,
Not a moment passed without teary eyes.
I wanted to freak out and scream,
Wishing that everything was just a fleeting, bad dream.

They say I will be fine
Since the two boys are mine.
But deep inside I feel so empty
Because the thought of you just won't leave me.

Then one Saturday, out of the blue,
The man I once admired came into view.
With him was a great armor for my defense
He said all His works will soon make sense.

I look up to that promise of Him
And have made myself draw nearer.
This curse will soon come to an end
And we would all forget it happened.

I just wish you get to know Him again
And let Him guide your way.
So you would then be free
And would never feel you are lonely.

The name you share with our kids, Brigz,
Will forever serve as a reminder.
That you are a part of them and me
And I will wait for the day you say, "We are still meant to be!"